

Explaining the Design Components of Residential Complexes Based on Responding to the Need for Self-Actualization (Case Study: Mabaas, Jannat, Modarres, Booali and Derak residential Complexes in Shiraz)*

Elahe Mohajer¹, Hamid Reza Azemati², Khosro Movahed³

1. Department of Architecture, Faculty of Art and Architecture, Shiraz Branch, Islamic Azad University, Shiraz, Iran

Email: Ellie.mohajer@gmail.com

2. (Corresponding author) Department of Architecture, Faculty of Architecture and Urban Design Engineering, Shahid Rajaei Teacher Training University, Tehran, Iran

Email: Azemati@sru.ac.ir

3. Department of Architecture and Urban Sustainability, University of the District of Columbia, Washington DC, USA

Email: Khosro.movahed@udc.edu

Article Info

Article type:
Research Article

Article History:

Received:

25 November 2023

Received in revised form:

26 February 2024

Accepted:

24 March 2024

Available online:

01 May 2024

Keywords:

Housing,

Residential Complexes,

Residential Complexes of Shiraz,

Self-Actualization

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, when societies are moving towards industrialization, it seems that the psychological dimensions of humans are disregarded. Self-actualization can be proposed as a solution to reduce the negative impacts caused by this. This motivation leads to improved psychological health and well-being in humans. It seems that spatial capabilities can be used to pursue self-actualization in people. Considering the mentioned necessity, this study aims to provide effective design components for responding to the self-actualization of residents in residential complexes. In the first step of the research's first phase, which is the document mining method, the sample population was available resources, and in the Delphi method, the sample population was 20 experts. The sample population in the second phase of the research to survey users was 290 residents of residential complexes in Shiraz city. Research was started using document mining and Delphi techniques, and sources were assessed. Then, experts were interviewed, and users were surveyed using the researcher-made questionnaire. Finally, the information obtained from the users' survey was entered into SPSS-23.0, and data analysis was performed using factor analysis and Pearson correlation tests. The findings of factor analysis present the components of creative space, collaborative space, environmental safety, event-figurative space, adaptive space, discoverable space, and engagement space as architectural components that are effective in responding to the self-actualization needs of residents of residential complexes, and the results of the correlation test show that all factors are positively and significantly correlated.

Cite this article: Mohajer, E., Azemati, H. R., & Movahed, K. (2024). Explaining the Design Components of Residential Complexes Based on Responding to the Need for Self-Actualization the Case Study A Mabaas, Jannat, Modarres, Booali and Derak residential Complexes in Shiraz. *Geographical Urban Planning Research Quarterly*, 12 (1), 43-61.

<http://doi.org/10.22059/JURBANGEO.2024.369557.1893>

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Publisher: University of Tehran Press

* This present article has been derived from Ms. Elahe Mohajer's Ph.D. thesis in the field of architecture under the supervision of the second author and the consultancy of the third author at the Faculty of Art and Architecture, Islamic Azad University, Shiraz branch.

Extended Abstract

Introduction

Nowadays, when societies are moving towards mechanization and humans' psychological aspects are more neglected than ever before, this lack of attention can cause feelings of emptiness, depression, and despair. Self-actualization can be proposed as a solution to reduce the damage caused by this. This motivation is one of the most important drivers for every person, so it can play a significant role in creating meaning and pleasure in human life. Considering this issue can improve people's psychological health and well-being. In this regard, it appears that spatial capabilities can be used in order to realize self-actualization. Due to the extensive relationship between humans and this space, the residential space can play an effective and significant role in achieving this aim. Considering the mentioned importance and necessity, the main question of the research can be raised as follows:

- What are the design components of residential complexes based on responding to the self-actualization needs of the residents?

Accordingly, this study has been conducted to provide effective design components to respond to the selfactualization of residents in residential complexes.

Methodology

The present study has been conducted using a combined approach, including quantitative and qualitative methods. In order to achieve the proposed goal and introduce the design components of residential complexes, this research is being conducted in two phases. The first phase consists of two steps, and the second phase contains one step. The first phase of the research was initiated by employing the document mining method and the Delphi technique. For this purpose, library and internet resources were scrutinized regarding the research topic. Then, in order to complete the information, experts in architecture, urban planning, psychology, and environmental psychology were interviewed, which ultimately led to the formation of a goal-objective table to design a research-made questionnaire for users. In the second phase, the users' questionnaire was designed using the users' goal-content table, which includes 58 questions with answers in the form of a 4- point Likert scale. Furthermore, its reliability has been confirmed by Cronbach's alpha, its formal validity by the theoretical consensus of experts, its content validity by using a goal-content table, and its structural validity by using R factor analysis. Finally, after

checking and verifying the researcher-made questionnaire, users are surveyed using the researcher-made questionnaire. The user survey information is entered into SPSS 23.0 statistical software, and data analysis is performed. At this stage, data analysis is done using "R factor analysis" and "Pearson's correlation" tests, which are performed to explore the design components of residential complexes based on the response to the need for selfactualization and check the correlation between the mentioned components. In the first step of the first phase of the research, which is the document mining method, the sample population is made up of available sources, and in the second step of the first phase of the research, which is the Delphi method, the sample population consists of 20 experts who were selected by the snowball method. In the second stage of the research, the sample population was calculated using Kline's point of view, which suggests between 5 and 6 people for each item of the questionnaire, so the sample population includes 290 residents of residential complexes in Shiraz. Five residential complexes in Shiraz were selected using cluster sampling to survey the users.

Results and discussion

The findings of the R factor analysis indicate that the needs of residential complex residents to achieve selfactualization are effectively fulfilled by the components of "creative space, collaborative space, safe environment, event-figurable space, adaptive space, discoverable space, and engagement space." According to the results of Pearson's correlation test, all components indicate a positive and significant association.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this research, it can be concluded that the components discovered in this research can play an effective role in achieving selfactualization in the residents of residential complexes. It can be acknowledged that in the space of residential complexes, the possibility of individual and collective participation in a creative and curious space can provide self-expression and self-reflection by giving freedom to act in the space; this ultimately provides the basis for people's self-actualization. In this regard, events formed in a adaptive and safe environment can create a creative and collaborative atmosphere and provide a platform for realizing the residents' selfactualization in residential complexes.

Funding

There is no funding support.

Authors' Contribution

The authors contributed equally to the conceptualization and writing of the article. All of the authors approved the content of the manuscript and agreed on all aspects of the work, with no declaration of competing interests.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgments

We are grateful to all the scientific consultants for this paper.

Ethics Approval and Consent to Participate

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The study was approved by Research Ethics Committees of Islamic Azad University (IR.IAU.A.REC.1403.135). Informed consent was obtained from all participants in the study.

Introduction

In the era of mechanization in societies, where the psychological dimensions of human beings have faded more than in the past, the concept of self-actualization can be proposed as a solution to the damage caused by this lack of attention. The answer to the need for self-actualization, because it reveals the identity and nature of the person, can provide the basis for facing human spiritual crises in contemporary culture. With the cross-cultural investigation of the values of societies, it was found that the metamaterial values, i.e., the needs of self-esteem and self-actualization, are becoming more important. In this regard, Inglehart suggests that sociologists consider the importance of self-actualization in today's societies (Inglehart, 2021). The need for self-actualization, which can be considered equal to self-realization, is a never-ending process of transformation that leads to the improvement of the state of human mental health (Schultz, 2022). In general terms, this need means the full realization of one's capabilities (D'Souza, 2018), and because this concept is seen as a motivation for growth (Thielke *et al.*, 2012), attention and response to the need for self-actualization is the main goal of every human being; it requires special attention in order to grow and improve human personality. Self-actualization can bring mental health and well-being to a person and give them a sense of enjoyment in life. In order to respond to this need, architectural spaces can play an important and fundamental role due to the continuous and constant communication of humans with these spaces.

In the process of designing and organizing housing spaces, which have always been more than a shelter for humans, factors such as people's culture, vision, and worldview have played an effective role in their formation (Barati, 2012: 25). It is necessary to pay attention to self-actualization as a need that humans are always looking to fulfill in order to increase the desirability of these spaces. On the other hand, the design of spaces without considering human needs will cause a lack of space, the impossibility of optimal control over the used spaces, and the impossibility of performing various activities in the space (Alaghemand *et al.*, 2018). Failure to pay attention to the need for self-actualization in an important space such as housing, due to the continuity of communication and the wide influence of this space on the residents, can cause a disruption in the formation of a positive and effective emotional connection between the person and the space.

Based on the stated importance and necessity, and with the need to pay attention to self-actualization as a necessity, the present research was written with the aim of exploring and explaining the design components of residential complexes based on residents' self-actualization. Despite the importance of responding to the need for self-actualization, this topic has not been adequately addressed in research related to the spaces of residential complexes. Therefore, exploring and explaining the design components of residential complexes in this research, in order to respond to the need for self-actualization, can be an effective and useful step in the path of personal growth and achieving self-actualization for residents of residential complexes. In order to achieve the stated goal, each of the introduced design components can include practical principles to design the spaces of residential complexes that increase the desirability of the spaces to achieve self-actualization and can be an architectural answer to this need. Finally, it can be acknowledged that the design of residential spaces can meet the needs of residents' self-actualization, while effective interaction between the individual and the housing space improves the desirability of the housing space, improves the quality of life and communication of the individual, and guarantees the well-being of individuals and society.

According to the raised issue, some questions have been formed in the minds of the researchers, which are:

First question: What are the architectural components of residential complexes based on residents' self-actualization?

Second question: What is the level of user agreement in each of the design components of residential complexes based on self-improvement?

The concept of self-actualization as an ancient and fundamental concept has long been discussed by many philosophers and theorists. This concept refers to the fundamental proverb of Socrates, namely: "Know yourself," which is a primary principle of Western thought (Marias, 2012). Also, the first manifestation of flourishing is evident in Aristotle's philosophical thinking, and the concept of "perfection" proposed by him refers to the full realization of potential. Accordingly, it is an ancient belief that every human being has unique potential that desires to be realized (Yalum, 2023: 394). In recent years, many researchers have examined this concept in their studies, which are mentioned below:

Interpersonal communication and self-actualization have been investigated in the research of Macklin and Rasitz (2009), and the results of this research indicate the existence of a meaningful and positive relationship between self-actualization and three communication variables. Also, Hanley and Abel (2003) present an interpersonal model of self-actualization in their research and emphasize the importance of social relationships on individual growth and self-actualization.

In order to examine the relationship between the artistic process and self-actualization, Manheim (2013) examines the role of creativity in personal growth and development in his research. The results of this study show that there is a relationship between the creation of 3D artwork and the development of self-actualization. Also, Ryder (1987) examines the relationship between self-actualization and the creative artistic process and suggests education through art as a factor of self-actualization. al-Muhammad *et al.* (2018), in their research, introduce components such as privacy and solitude, presence and sociability, and simplicity in organizing the environment as spatial attributes of public spaces in universities in order to respond to students' self-actualization needs.

Regarding the importance of paying attention to self-actualization in life, Zhang *et al.* (2019) found in their research that the most common desire of people in smart cities includes answering the need for self-actualization.

About the effect of the physical environment of education on the realization of students' potential talents, GholamAlizadeh and Mokhberi (2013) in their research suggest concepts such as the use of visual attractions and rich details, as well as innovative environmental values and qualitative concepts related to native and cultural patterns in the space, in the design of educational places.

Kovten (2014), in his research, while pointing out the importance of meeting the needs of the individual at three levels of biological, social, and self-actualization needs through architectural features, suggests principles for each of the levels of design.

In their research, D'Souza *et al.* (2015) examine the level of self-actualization in people and come to the conclusion that although a person may claim to have self-actualization values, internal factors do not necessarily show self-actualization behavior in life.

Pidrahita (2014) has conducted research in order to develop and support the ability of self-actualization from childhood and finally suggested some tips for design.

Regarding the relationship between learning and self-actualization, Selvi (2009) considers lifelong learning as a way to form a great environment and states that self-perception leads to learning and ultimately self-actualization.

The research of Neubauer *et al.* (2018) was written with the aim of investigating how creativity and intelligence are related to different levels of the hierarchy of human needs, and the results show that creativity has a positive relationship with high levels of human needs such as self-actualization.

Theoretical Foundations

The word "dwelling" in Dehkhoda's dictionary is defined as residence and peace, and its root is "sakan," which means to stay at home (Dehkhoda, 2015). Schultz believes that residence leads to establishing a meaningful connection with a given place (Schultz, 2023), and Markus considers the house as a symbol of the self (Markus, 2022:59). Based on this, the process of living in housing can be considered a metamaterial concept that is associated with the formation of deep and meaningful mutual relationships and ultimately forms an effective link between the person and the house. This space is one of the most important spaces around a person, and like any other space, in order to respond to human needs, it is necessary to plan and organize the structure of residential spaces to respond to all the needs of the residents.

In the built environment, the capabilities of the space are evaluated to respond and match the different levels of the user's needs, and if the environment does not match, the architectural attributes are changed according to the user's preferences and desires, and thus the environment adapts to the user through personalization (Fig. 1) (Asadpoor & Jusan, 2012).

Figure 1. Built environment personalization model (Asadpoor & Jusan, 2012)

The word "self-actualization" is defined in the Oxford dictionary as growing with vigor, progress, and prominence (Gokcen *et al.*, 2012: 4). It indicates that every human, in addition to having a set of intellectual capacities and potentials, also has an eternal and primary awareness of the existence of these potentials (Yalom, 2023: 394). In order to achieve self-actualization, one can take advantage of architectural capabilities (Weaver, 2010). In residential spaces, people's needs are met at different levels (Figure 2). Accordingly, the most ideal home is a "motivational home," which helps its residents achieve self-actualization. Because the environment, the residents of the house, and

their needs and desires change rapidly over time, the house needs a flexible spatial configuration that covers physical flexibility, social flexibility, and cultural flexibility (Estaji, 2014).

Figure 2. Different levels of housing based on response to needs theory (Estaji, 2014)

The purpose of the formation of architectural spaces at any level is to respond to a range of human needs, but the most important point is the necessity of designing architectural spaces by considering extra-material needs. Paying attention to self-actualization as a need can be effective in increasing the quality of housing and shaping desirable housing. In addition to this, achieving self-actualization leads to an increase in mental well-being, mental health, and the promotion of individual creativity. In this regard, residential complexes can effectively play a role in influencing self-actualization due to their dimensions.

Meanwhile, each of the spatial levels and spatial territories in residential complexes can have a significant contribution. In order to plan the design process of spaces based on responding to the need for self-actualization, identifying and explaining the design components effective for self-actualization in residential complexes is proposed as the first step towards achieving this goal.

In order to explain the theoretical scope of the research, the theoretical framework is presented in Figure 3:

Figure 3. The theoretical framework of the research

Research Methodology

The current research was written with the aim of explaining and exploring the design components of residential complexes based on the self-actualization of residents. According to the stated purpose, a mixed research method, including quantitative and qualitative methods, has been considered. In the present research, in the first phase, the sand mining method is used to review the literature. Following this, due to the fact that no questionnaire was found in previous studies in the area of the study, information was received from the experts after going through the steps of the Delphi method through an open-ended interview. Then, the open and central coding of the concepts was done, and the goal-content table was designed. Subsequently, using the goal-content table, the construction researcher questionnaire has been designed. In order to design the construction researcher questionnaire, examples of architecture have been presented according to each of the contents. After checking the validity of the research tool in the form of a 4-option questionnaire, including the options "completely agree" and "completely disagree," a survey of 290 residents of residential complexes in Shiraz was conducted. Finally, the information was analyzed by SPSS-23 software, using factor analysis tests to discover the effective factors and the Pearson correlation test to check the correlation coefficients between the factors. The process of carrying out different stages of the research can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Research process

Reliability of the research tool

In this research, reliability was measured by Cronbach's alpha, which is the most famous test for internal consistency reliability (Karimi, 2014). For the user questionnaire, a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.969 was calculated, which is considered "excellent," indicating an acceptable coefficient and the validity of the questionnaire. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Reliability confirmation of users' questionnaires by calculating Cronbach's alpha

Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Questions
.969	58

The studied community

In this research, in the first phase, to collect the literature on the subject, the statistical population consists of all relevant and available information sources. In the Delphi method, the opinions of 20 experts in the fields of architecture, urban planning, psychology, and environmental psychology have been used. The selection of the first candidates is done using the theoretical method, and for other experts, it is the snowball sampling method. Interviews with experts continued until theoretical saturation. In the user survey stage, the studied community consists of people living in large and medium-sized residential complexes, and the data source is a questionnaire. To calculate the sample size, despite the lack of general agreement regarding the calculation of the sample size for factor analysis (Schreiber *et al.*, 2006), many researchers suggest a minimum required sample size of 200 (Sivo *et al.*, 2006; Hoe, 2008). In this research, the sample population size is calculated based on Kline's opinion, which suggests a sample size of 5 to 2.5 people for each item in the questionnaire (Kline, 2023: 53). Therefore, for the current research, according to the number of questions in the questionnaire, which was 58 items, the sample size was 290 people. Questionnaires were distributed among the residents of five residential complexes in Shiraz city, including the residential complexes "Mabaat, Modares, Jannett, Darak, and Buali."

Findings and discussion

In this research, to achieve and discover the design components of residential complexes based on self-actualization, the first step of the first phase, titled sand exploration, involved a review of sources related to the research and the collection of basic concepts. Further, to complete this information in the second phase of the first step, interviews with experts were conducted using the Delphi method, followed by open coding of the concepts obtained from the interviews. The titles of the continuums resulting from open coding are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Open coding of concepts obtained from interviews with experts

1	Environmental comfort	4	Naturalism of the space	7	Spatial vitality	10	Sociability of the space	13	Environmental diversity
2	explorable space	5	Flexibility of the space	8	Environmental-social security	11	event-figurable space	14	Creativity of the space
3	Irritability of the space	6	Environmental participation	9	Spatial appeal	12	Ease of use of the space	15	Multi-functional space

In the following, axial coding was done, and the concepts resulting from the axial coding of the continuums include: "diverse and attractive space, social events, security and psycho-environmental comfort, searchable space, participatory space, and lively and creative space." These factors are used as goals in the goal-content table. Then, a questionnaire for experts was designed, and the Q factor analysis was performed on the questionnaires. The result of the KMO test was 0.783, indicating the very appropriate adequacy of the sample size, the significance of Bartlett's test, and the validity of the varimax rotation. According to the rotated data matrix, definable and meaningful factors can be identified. At this stage, five factors are deduced, which are introduced as the mental models of experts in the field of designing residential complexes. In Table 3, each dimension is presented along with the factor load of each component.

Table 3. Design dimensions of residential complexes along with the factor load of each component

Group number	title	Number of Experts	factor load
1st factor	Functional-activity	No. 9	0.764
		No. 12	0.671
		No. 10	0.611
		No. 8	0.609
		No. 5	0.604
		No. 13	0.537
2nd factor	Interactive	No. 3	0.433
		No. 19	0.686
		No. 1	0.632
3rd factor	Physical	No. 4	0.604
		No. 6	0.585
		No. 11	0.770
4th factor	Perceptual-semantic	No. 17	0.563
		No. 2	0.505
		No. 7	0.777
5th factor	Sensory-experiential	No. 14	0.591
		No. 20	0.800
		No. 18	-0.659
		No. 16	0.470

In the second phase (survey), a questionnaire is designed using the target-content table to survey the users. After the residents complete the questionnaires, the data is entered into the SPSS-23 software, and R factor analysis is used to analyze the data. At this stage, the value of the KMO index is equal to 0.928, so the adequacy of the sample size is very suitable, and the significance of Bartlett's sphericity test also confirms the factorial ability of the data (Table 4).

Table 4. KMO test and Bartlett's sphericity

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy		.928
Bartlett's test of sphericity	Approx Chi-Square	11138.750
	Df	1653
	.Sig	.000

Based on Table 5, which shows the variance of the rotated data, it can be concluded that the questions raised in the questionnaire are categorized into 11 factors, and the sum of the first 11 factors was able to explain 66.199% of the total variance.

Table 5. Data variance after factor analysis rotation

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	19.776	34.097	34.097	9.388	16.186	16.186
2	4.842	8.349	42.446	5.519	9.516	25.702
3	2.718	4.686	47.132	4.113	7.092	32.794
4	1.959	3.378	50.510	3.708	6.394	39.188
5	1.619	2.792	53.302	3.327	5.737	44.924
6	1.525	2.629	55.931	3.111	5.364	50.288
7	1.360	2.345	58.276	2.517	4.340	54.628
8	1.233	2.125	60.401	1.999	3.447	58.075
9	1.166	2.010	62.411	1.647	2.839	60.914
10	1.123	1.936	64.347	1.551	2.674	63.589
11	1.074	1.852	66.199	1.514	2.610	66.199

Among the 11 factors identified in the rotated data matrix, factors with three or more questions can be interpreted (Izquierdo *et al.*, 2014). Accordingly, factors 1 to 7 have

specific meanings and can be defined. After identifying the significant factors and the questions that are associated with them, each factor is defined and named. Table 6 shows the content of the questions for each component along with the factor load of each question.

Table 6. The content of the questions for each of the components, along with the factor load of each of the questions

Group number	question number	Content of questions	factor load
Component 1	24	Collective creative participation in the residential complex space	0.792
	22	The possibility of changing the facilities and environmental furniture according to the opinion of the residents	0.744
	25	The possibility of personalizing the space according to the taste of the residents	0.743
	1	Using flowers and fragrant plants and fruit trees in the spaces of the residential complex	0.730
	30	Evocative and memorable spaces of the complex	0.701
	26	The presence of various and attractive colors in the walls and bodies in order to visually attract the space	0.697
	20	Sensory richness and natural atmosphere using plants, fountains and birds	0.687
	29	The formation of a social learning environment for the individual development of the residents of the residential complex	0.686
	2	It is possible to observe the desirable and natural view in the residential units in order to make the space attractive for people	0.667
	33	The possibility of participation of residents in the events formed in the space	0.605
	7	The formation of solitude by defining the privacy of spaces for the psychological comfort of the residents	0.594
	6	Cozy and relaxing spaces in the natural space of the residential complex	0.569
	41	Desirable space design for doing creative team work in order to form a creative space for the residents	0.563
	9	Variety in the type and color of lighting in the residential complex space	0.512
	27	Formation of creative and enjoyable activities in the space	0.482
	12	The possibility of searching and exploring in the spaces of the residential complex	0.444
	5	The middle open space by taking advantage of the favorable nature with the possibility of free circulation and movement in it	0.397
	10	Utilizing symbolic and meaningful works of art in order to explore the space of the residential complex	0.377
48	The mobility of the space in order to form a lively space	0.332	
Component 2	57	The existence of a field and playground for sports and team games and the formation of exciting activities in the complex.	0.819
	58	The presence of sports equipment and walking and cycling paths in nature	0.778
	56	The existence of a space platform for holding family ceremonies and happy and lively events in the complex	0.698
	21	Formation of meaningful events in cultural occasions in the complex	0.684
	16	Desirable spaces for playing and activities of people in order to form a lively space in the complex environment	0.622
	46	Existence of spaces such as a small library and reading room in the complexes for the purpose of individual development of the residents	0.533
	11	Attractive middle open space designed to encourage residents to move and be in the space	0.407
	18	The formation of ritual and identity events in the residential complex	0.341
	23	The existence of a meeting hall in order to provide a context for social events in the complex	0.336
Component	36	The presence of environmental furniture with various shapes and functions	0.704

3	38	in the spaces of residential complexes Natural space with good furniture, to sit and watch the natural scenery	0.640
	39	A wide terrace with several chairs to sit facing the natural view, in residential units	0.577
	42	The formation of various activities in the residential complex	0.568
	37	Designing a green roof in order to be present and form social interactions in a residential complex	0.533
	55	The presence of various uses and activities in the space in order to give the right of choice to the residents	0.503
	35	The presence of communal and individual tables, benches and chairs in various colors in the natural open space	0.461
Component 4	50	The possibility of changing the shape of benches and chairs according to people's preferences and giving freedom of choice to residents	0.676
	51	Ease of working with the equipment available in the residential complex space	0.656
	52	The possibility of planting plants and trees in the cooperative garden	0.634
	53	The possibility of working comfortably and freely in the space of the residential complex	0.622
	49	Taking advantage of facilities and spaces that have multiple functions in order to give freedom in user choice	0.558
	54	Holding various events in the space of the residential complex in order to involve the residents in the space	0.495
Component 5	43	The existence of spaces that allow people to meet each other	0.666
	44	Spaces with benches and seats close together, in order to form friendly and intimate interactions between residents.	0.614
	45	Designing beautiful lobbies with several seats at the entrance of blocks and floors and encouraging residents to be present and interact in the space	0.602
	19	The formation of memorable collective events in the space	0.470
Component 6	32	The visibility of the routes and the ease of navigation in the residential complex space in order to provide mental comfort	0.683
	31	The possibility of monitoring public spaces in order to ensure the sense of security of the residents of the residential complex	0.610
	40	Preservation of people's privacy and provision of mental comfort for the residents of the residential complex	0.602
	28	The possibility of easy and free movement without hindrance in the space of the residential complex for the safety of people	0.556
Component 7	15	Ambiguity and mysteriousness of different spaces of the residential complex in order to make people curious	0.805
	13	Designing open spaces in a complex and explorable way	0.735
	47	Utilizing works of art and symbolic environmental elements in different spaces of the residential complex	0.480
	14	Designing the open space of the complex in an organic and natural way, in order to encourage the residents to search and move in the space	0.367

In the following, the naming of the concepts has been approved and reviewed by six experts. The components of "creative space," "event-figurable space," "adaptive space," "Collaborative space," "engagement space," "safe environment," and "explorability of the space" have been introduced as components of the design of residential complexes effective on the self-actualization of residents. The statistical information for the mentioned components is presented in Table 7:

Table 7. Mean and standard deviation of the design components of residential complexes based on residents' self-actualization

component	Minimum	Maximum	Mean		Std. Deviation	Variance
			Statistic	Std. Error		
creative space	1.16	4.00	3.5652	.02743	.46713	.218

event-figurable space	1.22	4.00	3.3735	.03474	.59163	.350
adaptive space	1.00	4.00	3.2664	.03794	.64615	.418
collaborative space	1.33	4.00	3.0314	.03751	.63877	.408
Engagement space	1.00	4.00	3.2101	.03973	.67661	.458
Safe environment	1.00	4.00	3.4164	.03440	.58582	.343
discoverable space	1.25	4.00	2.8413	.04092	.69688	.486

In this research, Pearson's coefficient was used to investigate the correlation between the design components of residential complexes based on self-actualization. The results of the correlation test can be seen in Table 8:

Table 8. Pearson correlation coefficient between each of the design components of the residential complex based on self-actualization

		creative space	event-figurable space	adaptive space	collaborative space	Engagement space	Safe environment	discoverable space
creative space	Pearson Correlation	1						
	Sig. (2-tailed)							
event-figurable space	Pearson Correlation	.625**	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000						
adaptive space	Pearson Correlation	.614**	.747**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000					
collaborative space	Pearson Correlation	.364**	.578**	.644**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000				
Engagement space	Pearson Correlation	.558**	.735**	.692**	.549**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000			
Safe environment	Pearson Correlation	.618**	.486**	.572**	.468**	.553**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		
discoverable space	Pearson Correlation	.312**	.393**	.484**	.537**	.512**	.434**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

According to the findings in Table 8, it can be acknowledged that there is a positive and significant relationship between all the design components of residential complexes, with each factor showing a meaningful correlation with the others. Next, the content of the questions related to these components will be discussed, and statistical information for each component will be presented:

Component 1: Creative Space: The factor of the creative space is identified as the first factor based on the content of the questions in the first group. Table 9 shows the level of agreement of the respondents with this concept.

Table 9. Description of the creative space factor

	Cumulative %	Percent	Frequency	Levels of agreement
Low agreement	2.4	2.4	7	Low agreement
Moderate agreement	6.9	4.5	13	Moderate agreement
High agreement	100.0	93.1	270	High agreement

Designing the spaces of residential complexes to incorporate nature, create a vibrant space, and include symbolic and meaningful works of art can foster a creative space. This component involves allowing residents to personalize and modify their space, giving them the freedom to intervene and participate in events, thus providing a platform for creativity among residents. Torrance (1965) emphasizes that nurturing personal creativity supports lifelong self-actualization (Burelson, 2005), making a

creative space essential for meeting the residents' need for self-actualization in residential complexes.

Component 2: Event-figurable space: According to the content of the questions, the second factor is named "event-figurable space." The level of agreement of the respondents with this concept can be seen in Table 10:

Table 10. Statistical description of the event-figurable space factor

	Cumulative %	Percent	Frequency	Levels of agreement
Low agreement	3.8	3.8	11	Low agreement
Moderate agreement	17.2	13.4	34	Moderate agreement
High agreement	100.0	82.8	240	High agreement

In the space of residential complexes, establishing platforms for meaningful rituals and identity events can create a backdrop for environmental activities. Researchers argue that cultural events enhance the spatial perception of areas (Richards & Palmer, 2012: 47). Additionally, well-designed central open spaces with walking and cycling paths can serve as venues for various activities within the community. According to researchers, events held within these spaces foster community cohesion and increase participation (Yahan and Wise, 2019). Therefore, event-figurable space is proposed as a component in the design of residential complexes aimed at promoting self-actualization, as it encourages participation, enriches environmental dynamics, and cultivates creativity.

Component 3: adaptive space: this component has been identified as the third factor. In Table 11, the level of agreement among users regarding this concept is presented.

Table 11. Statistical description of the adaptive space factor

	Cumulative %	Percent	Frequency	Levels of agreement
Low agreement	4.1	4.1	12	Low agreement
Moderate agreement	26.2	22.1	64	Moderate agreement
High agreement	100.0	73.8	214	High agreement

The element of adaptability in residential complex spaces can involve designing green roofs with furniture and pavilions that allow people to comfortably enjoy nature. Additionally, including spacious terraces facing natural surroundings with seating options in residential units can increase the presence of people in these spaces. Researchers acknowledge that spatial adaptability can significantly contribute to individual self-actualization by offering freedom of choice (Alaghemand *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, providing adaptive uses and facilitating various activities empowers residents to make choices that can enhance their self-actualization.

Component 4: Collaborative space: The factor of " Collaborative space " is identified as the fourth factor based on the questions in the fourth group. Table 12 illustrates the level of agreement among users regarding the concept of collaborative space.

Table 12. Statistical description of the collaborative space factor

	Cumulative %	Percent	Frequency	Levels of agreement
Low agreement	5.2	5.2	15	Low agreement
Moderate agreement	42.4	37.2	108	Moderate agreement
High agreement	100.0	57.6	167	High agreement

In the space of residential complexes, allowing residents freedom of movement and flexible spaces enables individuals to control and personalize their surroundings.

According to researchers, enabling personalization of spaces lays the foundation for achieving self-actualization (Alaghemand *et al.*, 2018; Lang, 2017). For instance, having a community garden in residential complexes that encourages resident participation can significantly contribute to this goal. Furthermore, hosting environmental events within these complexes can enhance community engagement with the space. Thus, fostering participation in residential complex spaces through opportunities for spatial control and self-expression meets residents' needs for self-actualization.

Component 5: Engagement space: The factor of "engagement space" is identified as the fifth factor based on the questions in this group. Table 13 presents the level of agreement among respondents regarding the concept of "engagement space."

Table 13. Statistical description of the factor of engagement space

	Cumulative %	Percent	Frequency	Levels of agreement
Low agreement	4.8	4.8	14	Low agreement
Moderate agreement	26.2	21.4	62	Moderate agreement
High agreement	100.0	73.8	214	High agreement

The components of engagement space include creating social and intimate spaces, providing areas with specific privacy featuring benches and chairs placed closely together, and enhancing opportunities for resident encounters. It also encompasses fostering friendly and genuine interactions among residents and organizing collective and memorable events that promote interaction among individuals. According to research, social communication is a key factor contributing to self-actualization (Hanley & Abell, 2003). Therefore, by realizing the component of engagement space within residential complex spaces, it becomes possible to establish the foundation for residents' achievement of self-actualization.

Component 6: Safe environment: The sixth factor is identified as safe environment based on the content of the questions in the sixth group. Table 14 presents the level of agreement among users regarding this component.

Table 14. Statistical description of safe environment factors

	Cumulative %	Percent	Frequency	Levels of agreement
Low agreement	2.4	2.4	7	Low agreement
Moderate agreement	15.5	13.1	38	Moderate agreement
High agreement	100.0	84.5	245	High agreement

The safe environment component encompasses concepts such as route visibility, ease of navigation, and unhindered movement within residential complex environments. It also involves the ability of complex management to monitor different spaces and ensure residents' privacy, thereby enhancing their security and psychological comfort. Researchers argue that residential spaces must provide varying levels of security to promote self-actualization (Seyfian and Mahmoudi, 2016). Therefore, ensuring security in residential complexes is considered a significant factor influencing residents' achievement of self-actualization.

Component 7: discoverable space: This factor, identified as the explorability factor based on the questions in the seventh group, is elaborated upon in descriptive detail in Table 15.

Table 15. Statistical description of the discoverable space factor

	Cumulative %	Percent	Frequency	Levels of agreement
Low agreement	9.3	9.3	27	Low agreement
Moderate agreement	54.1	44.8	130	Moderate agreement
High agreement	100.0	45.9	133	High agreement

This component is realized in the space through concepts such as the encryption and ambiguity of different spaces within residential complexes, which arouse curiosity and encourage exploration. The effect of complex organic spaces also stimulates individuals to explore their surroundings. Additionally, the use of art with symbolic meaning and the complexity and explorability of residential complex spaces further facilitate spatial exploration. According to Weaver (2010), the exploration process aids individuals in discovering the mysteries of their surroundings, which is essential for personal growth. Therefore, the explorability component of residential complex spaces can significantly influence residents' self-actualization.

The model of residential complex design components based on residents' self-actualization is presented in Figure 5:

Figure 5. Design components of residential complexes based on residents' self-actualization

Conclusion

Due to the importance of addressing the needs of metamaterials and their consideration at various levels of the space, especially within architectural spaces, this research explores and explains the design components of residential complexes with a focus on fulfilling residents' needs for self-actualization. To achieve this goal, the study employs sand mining, Delphi, and survey methods. The research identifies and elucidates key components of residential complex design that cater to residents' self-actualization needs: creative space, event-figurable space, adaptive space, collaborative space, engagement space, safe environment, discoverable space.

The application of these components in shaping residential spaces to meet self-actualization needs is emphasized. Safe environment, highlighted as a crucial component, involves planning residential complex designs that ensure specific, monitored privacy, promoting relaxation and clarity. This approach contributes significantly to mental security and comfort, crucial for achieving self-actualization goals.

These findings align with Sifian and Mahmoudi's (2016) research, emphasizing the role of comfort, environmental, and social security in architectural spaces for fostering self-actualization. Similarly, Weaver (2010) underscores the importance of spatial exploration and searchability in achieving self-actualization, advocating for the design of complex and explorable spaces that encourage contemplation and interaction with the space.

Additionally, the research identifies the creative space as another influential component for self-actualization, supporting Neubauer *et al.*'s (2018) findings. Creating a spatial platform within residential complexes that nurtures creativity involves empowering users to modify their space, fostering vibrant and creative activities among residents.

In the research of Qarabeglu *et al.* (2016), event-figurable space is introduced as one of the effective components of self-actualization, confirming this finding. Therefore, in residential complex spaces, planning spaces with the potential to host collaborative and creative events can provide the foundation for self-actualization. This research also introduces Collaborative space as a factor influencing self-actualization, where personalizing the space allows users the freedom to intervene and express themselves, leading to personal reflection within the space. This finding aligns with Lang's research (2017).

Furthermore, adaptability - the ability to accommodate adaptive functions in different spaces - is introduced as another component influencing residents' self-actualization. This component is also discussed by al-Muhamiz *et al.* (2018) as a factor impacting self-actualization. Lastly, fostering engagement space, as identified in this study, can influence residents' self-actualization. This component corroborates Hanley and Abell's (2003) research, emphasizing the creation of engagement spaces with appropriate privacy to facilitate intimate conversations and centralized furnishings to enhance social interactions.

Based on these findings, it is concluded that these components play significant roles in fostering self-actualization among residents of residential complexes. Therefore, facilitating individual and collective participation in a creative and stimulating space allows residents the freedom to express themselves, thereby contributing to their self-actualization. Events held in an adaptive and secure environment can cultivate a collaborative atmosphere, further supporting residents' self-actualization in residential complexes. These components collectively enhance the attractiveness of residential spaces for residents' well-being.

As suggestions for future research, similar studies could be conducted in other settings such as administrative, cultural, and educational environments, and among different age groups including children and teenagers.

Figure 6. Design components of residential complexes in order to respond to the need for self-actualization

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